

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

NICK C. CAIGA, MAEd

Instructor III

Pangasinan State University

ncaiga.sancarlos@psu.edu.ph

“WHEN LINES EXTEND”

Gone were the days when I was so little,
So little that I believe everything I was told.
From politics, philosophies, to axioms and truths;
As a sponge absorbs all that it approached.

Approaching numbers and figures dance as ocean waves,
I remember all the points, postulates, planes...
We talked about them every minute, that fateful day.
When I began unlearning things to learn anew.

And you know what's true about it all?
The shortest distance is a straight line!
But beyond that, I doubt if it's still true;
For there is more than a lot of points though.

I wasn't listening anyway, so why would I care...
They taught me a lot more than lines and planes,
Like the sounds of the pouring snow and rain,
It has patterns, soothing the pain of a longing saint.

Yet the shortest distance, it turned out
It is not a straight line, nor a curve,
But an empty space between two crowns,
Longing to be closer, despite the limits.

Limits of politics, rules and personal gains,
That no mathematical formulas could ever explain;
The distance it stretches in between
Like no other points and lines on a plane.

Still a lot to learn and relearn, I know
But that's the reason I don't waiver;

To keep moving forward forever –
Even when the lines extend further.

